

D10.3 Relevant standardization landscape and applicable standards

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Executive summary

The Spanish Association for Standardization (UNE), as a European Standardization Body, is a partner in the FATIGUE4LIGHT project to provide support regarding the standardization tasks included in the project. In order to fulfil this commitment, this deliverable, D10.3 "Relevant standardization landscape and applicable standards", has been prepared to guide the partners about the published standards and standards under development that can be applicable to FATIGUE4LIGHT.

This deliverable also contains, the fields of interest related to FATIGUE4LIGHT project, given by its consortium, and, from this starting point, identification and analysis of the standardization technical committees (TC) related with the project as well as of the published standards and standards under development that could be useful and relevant for the project activities.

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List of abbreviations

In this document the following abbreviations and acronyms could be used, and in this list, they are indicated with its meaning:

UNE	Spanish Association for Standardization
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CENELEC (CLC)	European Committee for Standardization in the Electrical field
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
CWA	CEN or CENELEC Workshop Agreement
EAD	European Assessment Document
EN	European Standard
EOTA	European Organisation for Technical Assessment
ESO	European Standardisation Organisation
ETAG	European Technical Approval Guideline
hEN	Harmonised European Standard
ISO	International Organization for Standardization; International Standard
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
NMC	National Mirror Committee
NSB	National Standardization Body
SC	Subcommittee
TC	Technical Committee
TR	Technical Report
TS	Technical Specification
WG	Working Group
WI	Work Item
ASD-STAN	AeroSpace and Defence Industries Association of Europe. Standardization
AECMA	Asociación Europea de Industrias Aeroespaciales

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Introduction

• Project Presentation Overview

FATIGUE4LIGHT project aims to investigate lightweight solutions adapted to the chassis part of EV to reach a 24-30% weight reduction. This will give a 12-15% weight saving from structural vehicle weight, and also increase EV safety due to reduced sprung mass. Solutions will be based on the introduction of especially developed material solutions with high fatigue performance (AHSS, stainless steel, Al alloys and hybrid metal-FRP materials), the development of new computer modelling with high fatigue prediction accuracy and new experimental methodologies that reduce the testing time.

Sustainability of the proposed solutions will be continuously considered along project through an eco-design general approach. Environmental assessments through LCA, affordability based in LCC as well as social inclusion thanks to the recovery of CRMs from alternative waste streams will allow endowing Fatigue4Light into a novelty circular dimension. Attention will be given to manufacturing processes (cutting and welding) to improve the knowledge on their effect to the overall fatigue performance of chassis components. Six lab scale and industrial demonstrators will be defined to validate the proposed solutions.

The fatigue model will be verified on demonstrators and then used in a virtual testing process to assess the weight reduction potential of the proposed materials, together with a redesign process oriented to lightweight the components while ensuring structural integrity. The Project will reduce lead times to market due to the developed model and advanced fatigue testing methodologies and standardization will be followed.

The final outcome is to give modelling and experimental tools for the lightweighting process on chassis parts subjected to fatigue. Clear and practical guidelines will be established with respect to different factors: eco design with proposed materials, advanced modelling approaches and the influence of forming processes on part performance.

• Attainment of the objectives and explanation of deviations

The deliverable is fully in line with the contractual obligations and the project objectives. There is no time and content deviation.

• Methodology of the document

This document presents the standardization activity found relevant for the FATIGUE4LIGHT project. In order to structure the research, a list of key concepts was elaborated by UNE to act as a starting point for the identification of standardization areas:

- Materials;
- Manufacturing
- Testing;
- Electric Vehicle;
- Life Cycle.

The standardization study covers European standardization developed by the European Committee for Standardization ([CEN](#)), the European Committee for electrotechnical Standardization ([CENELEC](#)) and the European Telecommunications Standards Institute ([ETSI](#)),

and also the International standardization developed by the International Organization for Standardization ([ISO](#)) and the International Electrotechnical Commission ([IEC](#)).

The study is structured in standardization areas for which relevant standardization technical committees (TCs) and other technical bodies within them, published standards and standards under development are referred.

• Short introduction about standardization

Standards are voluntary technical documents that set out requirements for a specific item, material, component, system or service, or describe in detail a particular method, procedure or best practice. Standards are developed and defined through a process of knowledge sharing and consensus building among technical experts nominated by interested parties and other stakeholders - including businesses, consumers and environmental groups, among others. These experts are organized in Technical Committees (TCs), which are subdivided in Subcommittees (SCs) or Working Groups (WGs). These TCs are included in the structure of the Standardization Organizations (National, European and International, with the respective mirror committees) and work following their internal regulations.

The standardization bodies operate at National (UNE, AFNOR, BSI, DIN, etc.), Regional (CEN, CENELEC, ETSI) or International (ISO, IEC, ITU) level. Sometimes there are different standardization bodies at the same level, but covering different fields. This is the case of ISO (general), IEC (electrical) and ITU (telecommunications) at International level, or CEN, CENELEC and ETSI at European level in the same way.

There are also different kinds of standardization documents. The most widespread is the standard, which has a different code depending on the organization under which it was developed; e.g. EN for European Standards, ISO or IEC for International standards. Other types of documents are Technical Specifications (TS), Technical Reports (TR) and Workshop Agreements (CWA). Further Amendments to the standards are identified by adding A1, A2, etc. at the end of the standard code.

At European level, all members of CEN and CENELEC shall adopt EN standards as national standards and shall withdraw any existing national standard which might conflict with them. A summary of the characteristics of the different standardization documents can be found in the following Table 1.

Table 1 – Characteristics of different standardization documents

Type	International code	European code	National code	Main characteristics
Standard	ISO IEC	EN	UNE, NF, BS, DIN, etc. When adopting: UNE-EN, NF-EN, UNE-ISO, NF-ISO, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elaboration: 3 years • 2 steps for member approval • European: compulsory national adoption Revision: every 5 years

Type	International code	European code	National code	Main characteristics
Technical Specification	ISO/TS IEC/TS	CEN/TS CLC/TS	When adopting: UNE-CEN/TS, NF-CEN/TS, UNE-ISO/TS, NF-ISO/TS, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elaboration: 21 months • 1 step for member approval or internal approval in TC • European: optional national adoption Revision: at 3 years (upgrading to EN or deletion)
Technical Report	ISO/TR IEC/TR	CEN/TR CLC/TR	When adopting: UNE-CEN/TR, NF-CEN/TR, UNE-ISO/TR, NF-ISO/TR, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elaboration: free timeframe • Internal approval in TC • European: optional national adoption No revision required
Workshop Agreement	IWA	CWA	Variable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elaboration: free timeframe (usually few months) • Internal approval in the Workshop • European: optional national adoption Revision: at 3 years (upgrading to EN or deletion)

There is also an agreement established between European and International Organizations (e.g. CEN and ISO) in order to avoid duplication of efforts and promote global relevance of standards, allowing the parallel adoption or development of standards with the same content and code. National standards could also be proposed as a base for new European or International standards. Figure 1 below shows the tracks of the standards.

Figure 1 – Possible tracks of standards adoption

Therefore, the code of any standard is the combination of the above-mentioned issues, and could be explained as shown in Figure 2:

Figure 2 – Example of identification of elements in the code of a standard

1. STANDARDIZATION RELATED TO FATIGUE4LIGHT PROJECT

1.1 Technical committees overview

1.1.1 Introduction

The following table lists the European and international committees which have been identified as technical bodies working on subjects related to the FATIGUE4LLIGHT project. Some of them cover only products or technical installations and thus may be considered as "vertical committees", and other cover common and repeatable basis in systems or management topics which could be named as "horizontal committees".

Table 2 – European and international committees related to FATIGUE4LLIGHT project

Subject	Technical committee
Materials	CEN/TC 132, Aluminium and aluminium alloys
	ASD-STAN/D 4, Materials
	CEN/TC 459, ECISS - European Committee for Iron and Steel Standardization
	CEN/TC 459/SC 5, Steels for heat treatment, alloy steels, free-cutting steels and stainless steels
	CEN/TC 459/SC 9, Coated and uncoated flat products to be used for cold forming
	ISO/TC 17, Steel
	ISO/TC 17/SC 3, Steels for structural purposes
	ISO/TC 17/SC 4, Heat treatable and alloy steels
	ISO/TC 17/SC 11, Steel castings
	ISO/TC 17/SC 12, Continuous mill flat rolled products
	CEN/TC 249, Plastics
	AECMA/SC, Aerospace
	ASD-STAN/MM, AeroSpace and Defence Industries Association of Europe. Standardization. Metallic Materials
Manufacturing	ISO/TC 44/SC 10, Quality management in the field of welding
	CEN/TC 121, Welding and allied processes
	ISO/TC 5/SC 5, Threaded fittings, solder fittings, welding fittings, pipe threads, thread gauges

Subject	Technical committee
	<p>ISO/TC 44, Welding and allied processes</p> <p>ISO/TC 44/SC 8, Equipment for gas welding, cutting and allied processes</p> <p>ISO/TC 44/SC 9, Health and safety</p> <p>ISO/TC 44/SC 10, Quality management in the field of welding</p> <p>ISO/TC 29/SC 9, Tools with defined cutting edges, holding tools, cutting items, adaptive items and interfaces</p> <p>CEN/TC 132, Aluminium and aluminium alloys</p> <p>ASD-STAN/D 4, Materials</p> <p>CEN/TC 459, ECISS - European Committee for Iron and Steel Standardization</p> <p>CEN/TC 459/SC 1, Test methods for steel (other than chemical analysis)</p> <p>CEN/TC 459/SC 3, Structural steels other than reinforcements</p> <p>CEN/TC 459/SC 9, Coated and uncoated flat products to be used for cold forming</p> <p>CEN/TC 459/SC 11, Steel castings and forgings</p> <p>ISO/TC 17/SC 11, Steel castings</p>
Testing	<p>ISO/TC 44/SC 5, Testing and inspection of welds</p> <p>ISO/TC 44/SC 6, Resistance welding and allied mechanical joining</p> <p>CEN/TC 250/SC 3, Eurocode 3 - Design of steel structures</p> <p>CEN/TC 249, Plastics</p> <p>ASD-STAN/SC</p> <p>CEN/SS M11, Pulvimetalurgia</p> <p>CEN/TC 262, Metallic and other inorganic coatings, including for corrosion protection and corrosion testing of metals and alloys</p> <p>CEN/TC 121, Welding and allied processes</p> <p>CEN/WS, Fateda</p> <p>ISO/TC 164/SC 4, Fatigue, fracture and toughness testing</p> <p>CEN/TC 459, ECISS - European Committee for Iron and Steel Standardization</p>
Electric Vehicle	<p>ISO/TC 22, Road vehicles</p> <p>ISO/TC 22/SC 33, Vehicle dynamics and chassis components</p> <p>ISO/TC 22/SC 34, Propulsion, powertrain and powertrain fluids</p>

Subject	Technical committee
	ISO/TC 22/SC 37, Electrically propelled vehicles
	ISO/TC 156, Corrosion of metals and alloys
Life Cycle	ISO/TC 59/SC 14, Design life
	ISO/TC 207/SC 5, Life cycle assessment
	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 7, Software and systems engineering

1.2 Materials

1.2.1 Introduction

In the field of Aluminium and aluminium alloys, Hi-Performance Steels, Stainless Steel and Composites, the standardization work related to FATIGUE4LIGHT is mainly developed at both European and International level. The following committees have been identified:

- CEN/TC 132, Aluminium and aluminium alloys
- ASD-STAN/D 4, Materials
- CEN/TC 459, ECISS - European Committee for Iron and Steel Standardization
- CEN/TC 459/SC 5, Steels for heat treatment, alloy steels, free-cutting steels and stainless steels
- CEN/TC 459/SC 9, Coated and uncoated flat products to be used for cold forming
- ISO/TC 17, Steel
- ISO/TC 17/SC 3, Steels for structural purposes
- ISO/TC 17/SC 4, Heat treatable and alloy steels
- ISO/TC 17/SC 11, Steel castings
- ISO/TC 17/SC 12, Continuous mill flat rolled products
- CEN/TC 249, Plastics
- AECMA/SC, Aerospace
- ASD-STAN/MM, AeroSpace and Defence Industries Association of Europe. Standardization. Metallic Materials

1.2.2 List of standards

Table 3 – Standards and project standards about Material

Reference	Document title
Aluminium and aluminium alloys	
EN 16914:2017	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Hot-rolled armour plates in weldable aluminium alloy - Technical delivery conditions
CEN/TR 16749:2014	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Classification of Defects and Imperfections in High Pressure, Low Pressure and Gravity Die Cast Products
CEN/TR 16748:2014	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Mechanical potential of Al-Si alloys for high pressure, low pressure and gravity die casting
EN 15530:2008	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Environmental aspects of aluminium products - General guidelines for their inclusion in standards
EN 13958:2008	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Cold drawn, round, coiled tube for general applications - Specification

Reference	Document title
EN 13957:2008	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Extruded round, coiled tube for general applications - Specification
EN 12482-2:1998	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Reroll stock for general applications - Part 2: Specifications for cold rolled reroll stock
EN 12482-1:1998	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Reroll stock for general applications - Part 1: Specifications for hot rolled reroll stock
EN 12258-2:2004	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Terms and definitions - Part 2: Chemical analysis
EN 12258-1:2012	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Terms and definitions - Part 1: General terms
EN 12020-2:2016	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Extruded precision profiles in alloys EN AW-6060 and EN AW-6063 - Part 2: Tolerances on dimensions and form
EN 12020-1:2008	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Extruded precision profiles in alloys EN AW-6060 and EN AW-6063 - Part 1: Technical conditions for inspection and delivery
EN 1780-3:2002	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Designation of alloyed aluminium ingots for remelting, master alloys and castings - Part 3: Writing rules for chemical composition
EN 1780-2:2002	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Designation of alloyed aluminium ingots for remelting, master alloys and castings - Part 2: Chemical symbol based designation system
EN 1780-1:2002	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Designation of alloyed aluminium ingots for remelting, master alloys and castings - Part 1: Numerical designation system
EN 1715-4:2008	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Drawing stock - Part 4: Specific requirements for welding applications
EN 1715-3:2008	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Drawing stock - Part 3: Specific requirements for mechanical uses (excluding welding)
EN 1715-2:2008	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Drawing stock - Part 2: Specific requirements for electrical applications
EN 1715-1:2008	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Drawing stock - Part 1: General requirements and technical conditions for inspection and delivery
EN 1706:2020+A1:2021	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Castings - Chemical composition and mechanical properties

Reference	Document title
EN 1669:1996	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Test methods - Earing test for sheet and strip
EN 1396:2015	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Coil coated sheet and strip for general applications - Specifications
EN 941:2014	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Circle and circle stock for the production of general applications - Specifications
EN 755-9:2016	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Extruded rod/bar, tube and profiles - Part 9: Profiles, tolerances on dimensions and form
EN 755-8:2016	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Extruded rod/bar, tube and profiles - Part 8: Porthole tubes, tolerances on dimensions and form
EN 755-7:2016	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Extruded rod/bar, tube and profiles - Part 7: Seamless tubes, tolerances on dimensions and form
EN 755-6:2008	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Extruded rod/bar, tube and profiles - Part 6: Hexagonal bars, tolerances on dimensions and form
EN 755-5:2008	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Extruded rod/bar, tube and profiles - Part 5: Rectangular bars, tolerances on dimensions and form
EN 755-4:2008	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Extruded rod/bar, tube and profiles - Part 4: Square bars, tolerances on dimensions and form
EN 755-3:2008	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Extruded rod/bar, tube and profiles - Part 3: Round bars, tolerances on dimensions and form
EN 755-2:2016	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Extruded rod/bar, tube and profiles - Part 2: Mechanical properties
EN 755-1:2016	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Extruded rod/bar, tube and profiles - Part 1: Technical conditions for inspection and delivery
EN 754-8:2016	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Cold drawn rod/bar and tube - Part 8: Porthole tubes, tolerances on dimensions and form
EN 754-7:2016	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Cold drawn rod/bar and tube - Part 7: Seamless tubes, tolerances on dimensions and form
EN 754-6:2008	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Cold drawn rod/bar and tube - Part 6: Hexagonal bars, tolerances on dimensions and form
EN 754-5:2008	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Cold drawn rod/bar and tube - Part 5: Rectangular bars, tolerances on dimensions and form
EN 754-4:2008	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Cold drawn rod/bar and tube - Part 4: Square bars, tolerances on dimensions and form

Reference	Document title
EN 754-3:2008	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Cold drawn rod/bar and tube - Part 3: Round bars, tolerances on dimensions and form
EN 754-2:2016	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Cold drawn rod/bar and tube - Part 2: Mechanical properties
EN 754-1:2016	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Cold drawn rod/bar and tube - Part 1: Technical conditions for inspection and delivery
EN 604-2:1997	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Cast forging stock - Part 2: Tolerances on dimensions and form
EN 604-1:1997	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Cast forging stock - Part 1: Technical conditions for inspection and delivery
EN 603-3:2021	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Wrought forging stock - Part 3: Tolerances on dimensions and form
EN 603-2:1996	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Wrought forging stock - Part 2: Mechanical properties
EN 603-1:1996	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Wrought forging stock - Part 1: Technical conditions for inspection and delivery
EN 586-3:2001	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Forgings - Part 3: Tolerances on dimensions and form
EN 586-2:1994	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Forgings - Part 2: Mechanical properties and additional property requirements
EN 586-1:1997	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Forgings - Part 1: Technical conditions for inspection and delivery
EN 575:1995	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Master alloys produced by melting - Specifications
EN 573-5:2007	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Chemical composition and form of wrought products - Part 5: Codification of standardized wrought products
EN 573-3:2019	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Chemical composition and form of wrought products - Part 3: Chemical composition and form of products
EN 573-2:1994	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Chemical composition and form of wrought products - Part 2: Chemical symbol based designation system
EN 573-1:2004	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Chemical composition and form of wrought products - Part 1: Numerical designation system
EN 570:2007	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Impact extrusion slugs obtained from wrought products - Specification

Reference	Document title
EN 515:2017	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Wrought products - Temper designations
EN 487:2009	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Rolling ingots - Specifications
EN 486:2009	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Extrusion ingots - Specifications
EN 485-4:1993	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Sheet, strip and plate - Part 4: Tolerances on shape and dimensions for cold-rolled products
EN 485-3:2003	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Sheet, strip and plate - Part 3: Tolerances on dimensions and form for hot-rolled products
EN 485-2:2016+A1:2018	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Sheet, strip and plate - Part 2: Mechanical properties
EN 485-1:2016	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Sheet, strip and plate - Part 1: Technical conditions for inspection and delivery
EN 4400-3:2019	Aerospace series - Aluminium and aluminium- and magnesium- alloys - Technical specification - Part 3: Aluminium and aluminium alloy bar and section
EN 4400-2:2019	Aerospace series - Aluminium and aluminium- and magnesium- alloys - Technical specification - Part 2: Aluminium and aluminium alloy sheet and strip
EN 4400-1:2019	Aerospace series - Aluminium and aluminium- and magnesium- alloys - Technical specification - Part 1: Aluminium and aluminium alloy plate
High-Performance Steels	
EN 10131:2006	Cold rolled uncoated and zinc or zinc-nickel electrolytically coated low carbon and high yield strength steel flat products for cold forming - Tolerances on dimensions and shape
EN 10025-1:2004	Hot rolled products of structural steels - Part 1: General technical delivery conditions
EN 10025-6:2019	Hot rolled products of structural steels - Part 6: Technical delivery conditions for flat products of high yield strength structural steels in the quenched and tempered condition
EN 10149-1:2013	Hot rolled flat products made of high yield strength steels for cold forming - Part 1: General technical delivery conditions
EN 10149-2:2013	Hot rolled flat products made of high yield strength steels for cold forming - Part 2: Technical delivery conditions for thermomechanically rolled steels

Reference	Document title
EN 10149-3:2013	Hot rolled flat products made of high yield strength steels for cold forming - Part 3: Technical delivery conditions for normalized or normalized rolled steels
EN 10210-3:2020	Hot finished steel structural hollow sections - Part 3: Technical delivery conditions for high strength and weather resistant steels
EN 10219-3:2020	Cold formed welded steel structural hollow sections - Part 3: Technical delivery conditions for high strength and weather resistant steels
ISO 6930:2019	High yield strength steel plates and wide flats for cold forming — Delivery conditions
ISO 14590:2016	Cold-reduced steel sheet of high tensile strength and low yield point with improved formability
ISO 4997:2015	Cold-reduced carbon steel sheet of structural quality
ISO 4951-1:2001	High yield strength steel bars and sections — Part 1: General delivery requirements
ISO 4951-2:2001	High yield strength steel bars and sections — Part 2: Delivery conditions for normalized, normalized rolled and as-rolled steels
ISO 4951-3:2001	High yield strength steel bars and sections — Part 3: Delivery conditions for thermomechanically-rolled steels
ISO 630-4:2021	Structural steels — Part 4: Technical delivery conditions for high yield strength quenched and tempered structural steel plates and wide flats
ISO 9477:2015	High strength cast steels for general engineering and structural purposes
ISO 5952:2019	Steel sheet, hot-rolled, of structural quality with improved atmospheric corrosion resistance
ISO 13887:2017	Steel sheet, cold-reduced, of higher yield strength with improved formability
ISO 4950-1:1995	High yield strength flat steel products — Part 1: General requirements
ISO 4950-2:1995	High yield strength flat steel products — Part 2: Products supplied in the normalized or controlled rolled condition
ISO 4950-3:1995	High yield strength flat steel products — Part 3: Products supplied in the heat-treated (quenched + tempered) condition
ISO/TS 4949:2016	Steel names based on letter symbols
ISO 20805:2017	Hot-rolled steel sheet in coils of higher yield strength with improved formability and heavy thickness for cold forming
ISO 15179:2012	Hot-rolled twin-roll cast steel sheet of structural quality and high strength steel

Reference	Document title
ISO 5951:2013	Hot-rolled steel sheet of higher yield strength with improved formability
Stainless Steel	
EN ISO 18286:2010	Hot-rolled stainless steel plates - Tolerances on dimensions and shape (ISO 18286:2008)
EN 10088-1:2014	Stainless steels - Part 1: List of stainless steels
EN 10088-2:2014	Stainless steels - Part 2: Technical delivery conditions for sheet/plate and strip of corrosion resisting steels for general purposes
EN 10088-3:2014	Stainless steels - Part 3: Technical delivery conditions for semi-finished products, bars, rods, wire, sections and bright products of corrosion resisting steels for general purposes
ISO 16143-1:2014	Stainless steels for general purposes — Part 1: Corrosion-resistant flat products
ISO 16143-2:2014	Stainless steels for general purposes — Part 2: Corrosion-resistant semi-finished products, bars, rods and sections
ISO 15510:2014	Stainless steels — Chemical composition
ISO 9444-1:2009	Continuously hot-rolled stainless steel — Tolerances on dimensions and form — Part 1: Narrow strip and cut lengths
ISO 9444-2:2009	Continuously hot-rolled stainless steel — Tolerances on dimensions and form — Part 2: Wide strip and sheet/plate
ISO 3651-1:1998	Determination of resistance to intergranular corrosion of stainless steels — Part 1: Austenitic and ferritic-austenitic (duplex) stainless steels — Corrosion test in nitric acid medium by measurement of loss in mass (Huey test)
ISO 3651-2:1998	Determination of resistance to intergranular corrosion of stainless steels — Part 2: Ferritic, austenitic and ferritic-austenitic (duplex) stainless steels — Corrosion test in media containing sulfuric acid
ISO 3651-3:2017	Determination of resistance to intergranular corrosion of stainless steels — Part 3: Corrosion test for low-Cr ferritic stainless steels
ISO 9445-1:2009	Continuously cold-rolled stainless steel — Tolerances on dimensions and form — Part 1: Narrow strip and cut lengths
ISO 9445-2:2009	Continuously cold-rolled stainless steel — Tolerances on dimensions and form — Part 2: Wide strip and plate/sheet

Reference	Document title
Composites	
EN 16245-1:2013	Fibre-reinforced plastic composites - Declaration of raw material characteristics - Part 1: General requirements
EN 16245-2:2013	Fibre-reinforced plastic composites - Declaration of raw material characteristics - Part 2: Specific requirements for resin, curing systems, additives and modifiers
EN 16245-3:2013	Fibre-reinforced plastic composites - Declaration of raw material characteristics - Part 3: Specific requirements for fibre
EN 16245-4:2013	Fibre-reinforced plastic composites - Declaration of raw material characteristics - Part 4: Specific requirements for fabrics
EN 16245-5:2013	Fibre-reinforced plastic composites - Declaration of raw material characteristics - Part 5: Specific requirements for core materials
EN 2374:1991	Aerospace series. glass fibre reinforced moulding and sandwich composites. Production of test panels.
EN 3783:2013	Aerospace series — Fibre composite materials — Normalisation of fibre dominated mechanical properties
EN 4408-001:2005	Aerospace series - Technical drawings - Representation of parts made of composite materials
EN 4408-002:2005	Aerospace series - Technical drawings - Representation of parts made of composite materials - Part 2: Laminated parts
EN 4408-003:2005	Aerospace series - Technical drawings - Representation of parts made of composite materials - Part 3: Parts including core materials
EN 4408-004:2005	Aerospace series - Technical drawings - Representation of parts made of composite materials - Part 4: Items obtained by winding
EN 4408-005:2005	Aerospace series - Technical drawings - Representation of parts made of composite materials - Part 5: Seams
EN 4408-006:2005	Aerospace series - Technical drawings - Representation of parts made of composite materials - Part 6: Preforms
EN 4866:2021	Aerospace series - Definitions of imperfections and defects in organic matrix composite materials
EN ISO 527-1:2019	Plastics - Determination of tensile properties - Part 1: General principles (ISO 527-1:2019)

Reference	Document title
EN ISO 527-4:1997	Plastics - Determination of tensile properties - Part 4: Test conditions for isotropic and orthotropic fibre-reinforced plastic composites (ISO 527-4:1997)
EN ISO 527-5:2009	Plastics - Determination of tensile properties - Part 5: Test conditions for unidirectional fibre-reinforced plastic composites (ISO 527-5:2009)
EN 12576:1998	Plastics - Fibre reinforced composites - Preparation of compression moulded test plates of SMC, BMC and DMC.
EN 13421:2006	Plastics - Thermoset moulding compounds - Composites and reinforcement fibres - Preparation of specimens for determining the anisotropy of the properties of compression moulding composites
EN 13706-1:2002	Reinforced plastics composites - Specifications for pultruded profiles - Part 1: Designation
EN 13706-2:2002	Reinforced plastics composites - Specifications for pultruded profiles - Part 2: Methods of test and general requirements
EN 13706-3:2002	Reinforced plastics composites - Specifications for pultruded profiles - Part 3: Specific requirements
EN ISO 14125:1998	Fibre-reinforced plastics composites. Determination of flexural properties (ISO 14125:1998)
EN ISO 14126:1999	Fibre reinforced plastic composites. Determination of compressive properties in the in-plane direction (ISO 14126:1999)
EN ISO 14129:1997	Fibre-reinforced plastic composites. Determination of in-plane shear stress/shear strain response, including the in-plane shear modulus and strength, by the +/- 45° tension test method (ISO 14129:1997)
EN ISO 14130:1997	Fibre-reinforced plastics composites. Determination of apparent interlaminar shear strength by short-beam method (ISO 14130:1997)
EN ISO 15310:2005	Fibre-reinforced plastic composites - Determination of the in-plane shear modulus by the plate twist method (ISO 15310:1999)
EN 17129:2018	Continuous-fibre-reinforced plastic composites - Pultruded unidirectional rods - Determination of tensile properties in parallel to the fibre direction
EN ISO 25762:2012	Plastics - Guidance on the assessment of the fire characteristics and fire performance of fibre-reinforced polymer composites (ISO 25762:2009)

1.3 Manufacturing

1.3.1 Introduction

In the field of Manufacturing (Welding, Cutting, Forging and Forming), the standardization work related to FATIGUE4LIGHT is mainly developed at both European and International level. The following committees have been identified:

- ISO/TC 44/SC 10, Quality management in the field of welding
- CEN/TC 121, Welding and allied processes
- ISO/TC 5/SC 5, Threaded fittings, solder fittings, welding fittings, pipe threads, thread gauges
- ISO/TC 44, Welding and allied processes
- ISO/TC 44/SC 8, Equipment for gas welding, cutting and allied processes
- ISO/TC 44/SC 9, Health and safety
- ISO/TC 44/SC 10, Quality management in the field of welding
- ISO/TC 29/SC 9, Tools with defined cutting edges, holding tools, cutting items, adaptive items and interfaces
- CEN/TC 132, Aluminium and aluminium alloys
- ASD-STAN/D 4, Materials
- CEN/TC 459, ECISS - European Committee for Iron and Steel Standardization
- CEN/TC 459/SC 1, Test methods for steel (other than chemical analysis)
- CEN/TC 459/SC 3, Structural steels other than reinforcements
- CEN/TC 459/SC 9, Coated and uncoated flat products to be used for cold forming
- CEN/TC 459/SC 11, Steel castings and forgings
- ISO/TC 17/SC 11, Steel castings

1.3.2 List of standards

Table 4 – Standards and project standards about Manufacturing

Reference	Document title
Welding	
ISO/TR 17844:2004	Welding — Comparison of standardised methods for the avoidance of cold cracks
EN 4632-001:2008	Aerospace series - Welded and brazed assemblies for aerospace constructions - Weldability and brazeability of materials - Part 001: General requirements
ISO/TR 17671-1:2002	Welding — Recommendations for welding of metallic materials — Part 1: General guidance for arc welding
ISO/TR 17671-2:2002	Welding — Recommendations for welding of metallic materials — Part 2: Arc welding of ferritic steels

Reference	Document title
ISO/TR 17671-5:2004	Welding — Recommendations for welding of metallic materials — Part 5: Welding of clad steels
ISO/TR 17671-6:2005	Welding — Recommendations for welding of metallic materials — Part 6: Laser beam welding
ISO/TR 17671-7:2004	Welding — Recommendations for welding of metallic materials — Part 7: Electron beam welding
ISO/TR 15608:2017	Welding — Guidelines for a metallic materials grouping system
EN 1011-1:2009	Welding - Recommendations for welding of metallic materials - Part 1: General guidance for arc welding
EN 1011-6:2018	Welding - Recommendation for welding of metallic materials - Part 6: Laser beam welding
EN 1011-7:2004	Welding - Recommendations for welding of metallic materials - Part 7: Electron beam welding
EN 1011-8:2018	Welding - Recommendations for welding of metallic materials - Part 8: Welding of cast irons
EN ISO 15616-1:2003	Acceptance tests for CO ₂ -laser beam machines for high quality welding and cutting - Part 1: General principles, acceptance conditions (ISO 15616-1:2003)
EN ISO 15616-2:2003	Acceptance tests for CO ₂ -laser beam machines for high quality welding and cutting - Part 2: Measurement of static and dynamic accuracy (ISO 15616-2:2003)
EN ISO 15616-3:2003	Acceptance tests for CO ₂ -laser beam machines for high quality welding and cutting - Part 3: Calibration of instruments for measurement of gas flow and pressure (ISO 15616-3:2003)
EN ISO 15616-4:2021	Acceptance tests for CO ₂ -laser beam machines for high quality welding and cutting - Part 4: Machines with 2-D moving optics (ISO 15616-4:2008)
ISO 11970:2016	Specification and qualification of welding procedures for production welding of steel castings
Welding - Aluminium and aluminium alloys	
EN 4632-002:2008	Aerospace series - Welded and brazed assemblies for aerospace constructions - Weldability and brazeability of materials - Part 002: Homogeneous assemblies aluminium and aluminium alloys
EN 4341:2001	Aerospace series - Aluminium alloy AL-W46431 - Filler metal for welding - Wire and rod
EN 4324:2001	Aerospace series. Aluminium alloy AL-W42201. Filler metal for welding. Rod

Reference	Document title
ISO/TR 17671-4:2002	Welding — Recommendations for welding of metallic materials — Part 4: Arc welding of aluminium and aluminium alloys
EN 1011-4:2000	Welding - Recommendations for welding of metallic materials - Part 4: Arc welding of aluminium and aluminium alloys
Welding - High-Performance Steels	
EN 1011-2:2001	Welding - Recommendations for welding of metallic materials - Part 2: Arc welding of ferritic steels
EN 4632-004:2012	Aerospace series - Weldability and brazeability of materials in aerospace constructions - Part 004: Welding and brazing of homogeneous assemblies of high alloyed steels
EN ISO 16834:2012	Welding consumables - Wire electrodes, wires, rods and deposits for gas shielded arc welding of high strength steels - Classification (ISO 16834:2012)
EN ISO 18275:2018	Welding consumables - Covered electrodes for manual metal arc welding of high-strength steels - Classification (ISO 18275:2018)
EN ISO 18276:2017	Welding consumables - Tubular cored electrodes for gas-shielded and non-gas-shielded metal arc welding of high strength steels - Classification (ISO 18276:2017)
EN ISO 26304:2018	Welding consumables - Solid wire electrodes, tubular cored electrodes and electrode-flux combinations for submerged arc welding of high strength steels - Classification (ISO 26304:2017)
Welding – Stainless Steels	
ISO/TR 17671-3:2002	Welding — Recommendations for welding of metallic materials — Part 3: Arc welding of stainless steels
ISO 5251:1981	Stainless steel butt-welding fittings
EN 1011-3:2018	Welding - Recommendations for welding of metallic materials - Part 3: Arc welding of stainless steels
EN ISO 3581:2016	Welding consumables - Covered electrodes for manual metal arc welding of stainless and heat-resisting steels - Classification (ISO 3581:2016, Corrected version 2017-11-01)
EN ISO 14343:2017	Welding consumables - Wire electrodes, strip electrodes, wires and rods for arc welding of stainless and heat resisting steels - Classification (ISO 14343:2017)
EN ISO 17633:2018	Welding consumables - Tubular cored electrodes and rods for gas shielded and non-gas shielded metal arc welding of stainless and heat-resisting steels - Classification (ISO 17633:2017)

Reference	Document title
Cutting	
EN ISO 7287:2002	Graphical symbols for thermal cutting equipment (ISO 7287:2002)
EN ISO 9013:2017	Thermal cutting - Classification of thermal cuts - Geometrical product specification and quality tolerances (ISO 9013:2017)
EN ISO 15616-1:2003	Acceptance tests for CO ₂ -laser beam machines for high quality welding and cutting - Part 1: General principles, acceptance conditions (ISO 15616-1:2003)
EN ISO 15616-2:2003	Acceptance tests for CO ₂ -laser beam machines for high quality welding and cutting - Part 2: Measurement of static and dynamic accuracy (ISO 15616-2:2003)
EN ISO 15616-3:2003	Acceptance tests for CO ₂ -laser beam machines for high quality welding and cutting - Part 3: Calibration of instruments for measurement of gas flow and pressure (ISO 15616-3:2003)
ISO 15616-4:2021	Acceptance tests for CO ₂ -laser beam machines for high quality welding and cutting - Part 4: Machines with 2-D moving optics (ISO 15616-4:2008)
EN ISO 17916:2016	Safety of thermal cutting machines (ISO 17916:2016)
EN 28206:1992	Acceptance tests for oxygen cutting machines. Reproducible accuracy. operational characteristics
ISO 11054:2006	Cutting tools — Designation of high-speed steel groups
ISO 513:2012	Classification and application of hard cutting materials for metal removal with defined cutting edges — Designation of the main groups and groups of application
Forging	
EN 10228-1:2016	Non-destructive testing of steel forgings - Part 1: Magnetic particle inspection
EN 10228-2:2016	Non-destructive testing of steel forgings - Part 2: Penetrant testing
EN 10228-3:2016	Non-destructive testing of steel forgings - Part 3: Ultrasonic testing of ferritic or martensitic steel forgings
EN 10250-1:1999	Open die steel forgings for general engineering purposes. Part 1: General requirements

Reference	Document title
EN 10250-2:1999	Open die steel forgings for general engineering purposes - Part 2: Non-alloy quality and special steels.
EN 10250-3:1999	Open die steel forgings for general engineering purposes. Part 3: alloy special steels.
Forging - Aluminium and aluminium alloys	
EN 603-1:1996	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Wrought forging stock - Part 1: Technical conditions for inspection and delivery
EN 603-2:1996	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Wrought forging stock - Part 2: Mechanical properties
EN 603-3:2000	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Wrought forging stock - Part 3: Tolerances on dimensions and form
EN 604-1:1997	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Cast forging stock - Part 1: Technical conditions for inspection and delivery
EN 604-2:1997	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Cast forging stock - Part 2: Tolerances on dimensions and form
EN 586-1:1997	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Forgings - Part 1: Technical conditions for inspection and delivery
EN 586-2:1994	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Forgings - Part 2: Mechanical properties and additional property requirements
EN 586-3:2001	Aluminium and aluminium alloys - Forgings - Part 3: Tolerances on dimensions and form
EN 4400-6:2019	Aerospace series - Aluminium and aluminium- and magnesium- alloys - Technical specification - Part 6: Aluminium alloy forging stock
Forging – Stainless Steels	
EN 10228-4:2016	Non-destructive testing of steel forgings - Part 4: Ultrasonic testing of austenitic and austenitic-ferritic stainless steel forgings
EN 10250-4:2021	Open die steel forgings for general engineering purposes - Part 4: Stainless steels
Forming	
EN 10111:2008	Continuously hot rolled low carbon steel sheet and strip for cold forming - Technical delivery conditions

Reference	Document title
EN 10130:2006	Cold rolled low carbon steel flat products for cold forming - Technical delivery conditions
EN 10139:2016+A1:2020	Cold rolled uncoated low carbon steel narrow strip for cold forming - Technical delivery conditions
EN 10338:2015	Hot rolled and cold rolled non-coated products of multiphase steels for cold forming - Technical delivery conditions
CEN/TR 10347:2006	Guidance for forming of structural steels in processing
EN ISO 12004-1:2020	Metallic materials - Determination of forming-limit curves for sheet and strip - Part 1: Measurement and application of forming-limit diagrams in the press shop (ISO 12004-1:2020)
EN ISO 12004-2:2021	Metallic materials - Determination of forming-limit curves for sheet and strip - Part 2: Determination of forming-limit curves in the laboratory (ISO 12004-2:2021)
Forming - High-Performance Steels	
EN 10131:2006	Cold rolled uncoated and zinc or zinc-nickel electrolytically coated low carbon and high yield strength steel flat products for cold forming - Tolerances on dimensions and shape
EN 10149-1:2013	Hot rolled flat products made of high yield strength steels for cold forming - Part 1: General technical delivery conditions
EN 10149-2:2013	Hot rolled flat products made of high yield strength steels for cold forming - Part 2: Technical delivery conditions for thermomechanically rolled steels
EN 10149-3:2013	Hot rolled flat products made of high yield strength steels for cold forming - Part 3: Technical delivery conditions for normalized or normalized rolled steels
EN 10268:2006+A1:2013	Cold rolled steel flat products with high yield strength for cold forming - Technical delivery conditions

1.4 Testing

1.4.1 Introduction

In the field of testing (mainly referred to fatigue testing), the standardization work related to FATIGUE4LIGHT is mainly developed at both European and International level. The following committees have been identified:

- ISO/TC 44/SC 5, Testing and inspection of welds
- ISO/TC 44/SC 6, Resistance welding and allied mechanical joining
- CEN/TC 250/SC 3, Eurocode 3 - Design of steel structures
- CEN/TC 249, Plastics
- ASD-STAN/SC
- CEN/SS M11, Pulvimetalurgia
- CEN/TC 262, Metallic and other inorganic coatings, including for corrosion protection and corrosion testing of metals and alloys
- CEN/TC 121, Welding and allied processes
- CEN/WS, Fateda
- ISO/TC 164/SC 4, Fatigue, fracture and toughness testing
- CEN/TC 459, ECISS - European Committee for Iron and Steel Standardization

1.4.2 List of standards

Table 5 – Standards and project standards about Testing

Reference	Document title
ISO/TS 20273:2017	Guidelines on weld quality in relationship to fatigue strength
ISO/TR 12998:2019	Mechanical joining — Guidelines for fatigue testing of joints
EN 1993-1-9:2005	Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures - Part 1-9: Fatigue
EN 1999-1-3:2007	Eurocode 9: Design of aluminium structures – Part 1-3: Structures susceptible to fatigue
EN ISO 3385:2014	Flexible cellular polymeric materials - Determination of fatigue by constant-load pounding (ISO 3385:2014)
EN 3873:2010	Aerospace series - Test methods for metallic materials - Determination of fatigue crack growth rates using Corner-Cracked (CC) test pieces
EN 3987:2009	Aerospace series - Test methods for metallic materials - Constant amplitude force-controlled high cycle fatigue testing
EN ISO 3928:2016	Sintered metal materials, excluding hardmetals - Fatigue test pieces (ISO 3928:2016)
EN 6072:2010	Aerospace series - Metallic materials - Test methods - Constant amplitude fatigue testing

Reference	Document title
EN ISO 11782-1:2008	Corrosion of metals and alloys - Corrosion fatigue testing - Part 1: Cycles to failure testing (ISO 11782-1:1998)
EN ISO 11782-2:2008	Corrosion of metals and alloys - Corrosion fatigue testing - Part 2: Crack propagation testing using precracked specimens (ISO 11782-2:1998)
EN ISO 14324:2003	Resistance spot welding - Destructive tests of welds - Method for the fatigue testing of spot welded joints (ISO 14324:2003)
EN ISO 18592:2019	Resistance welding - Destructive testing of welds - Method for the fatigue testing of multi-spot-welded specimens (ISO 18592:2019)
CWA 17157:2017	Engineering materials - Electronic data interchange - Formats for fatigue test data
ISO 27306:2016	Metallic materials — Method of constraint loss correction of CTOD fracture toughness for fracture assessment of steel components
ISO 1099:2017	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Axial force-controlled method
ISO 1143:2010	Metallic materials — Rotating bar bending fatigue testing
ISO 1352:2011	Metallic materials — Torque-controlled fatigue testing
ISO 4965-1:2012	Metallic materials — Dynamic force calibration for uniaxial fatigue testing — Part 1: Testing systems
ISO 4965-2:2012	Metallic materials — Dynamic force calibration for uniaxial fatigue testing — Part 2: Dynamic calibration device (DCD) instrumentation
ISO 9015-1:2001	Destructive tests on welds in metallic materials — Hardness testing — Part 1: Hardness test on arc welded joints
ISO 9015-2:2016	Destructive tests on welds in metallic materials — Hardness testing — Part 2: Microhardness testing of welded joints
ISO 12106:2017	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Axial-strain-controlled method
ISO 12107:2012	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Statistical planning and analysis of data
ISO 12108:2018	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Fatigue crack growth method
ISO 12110-1:2013	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Variable amplitude fatigue testing — Part 1: General principles, test method and reporting requirements
ISO 12110-2:2013	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Variable amplitude fatigue testing — Part 2: Cycle counting and related data reduction methods
ISO 12111:2011	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Strain-controlled thermomechanical fatigue testing method
ISO/TR 12112:2018	Metallic materials — Principles and designs for multiaxial fatigue testing

Reference	Document title
ISO 22407:2021	Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Axial plane bending method
ISO 23788:2012	Metallic materials — Verification of the alignment of fatigue testing machines
ISO 27306:2016	Metallic materials — Method of constraint loss correction of CTOD fracture toughness for fracture assessment of steel components
EN ISO 2566-1:1999	Steel. Conversion of elongation values. Part 1: Carbon and low alloy steels (ISO 2566-1:1984).
EN ISO 2566-2:1999	Steel. Conversion of elongation values. Part 2: Austenitic steels (ISO 2566-2:1984).

1.5 Electric Vehicle

1.5.1 Introduction

In the field of Electric Vehicles, the standardization work related to FATIGUE4LIGHT scope is mainly developed at International level. The following committees have been identified:

- ISO/TC 22, Road vehicles
- ISO/TC 22/SC 33, Vehicle dynamics and chassis components
- ISO/TC 22/SC 34, Propulsion, powertrain and powertrain fluids
- ISO/TC 22/SC 37, Electrically propelled vehicles
- ISO/TC 156, Corrosion of metals and alloys

1.5.2 List of standards

Table 6 – Standards and project standards about Electric Vehicle

Reference	Document title
ISO/TR 8713:2019	Electrically propelled road vehicles — Vocabulary
ISO/DIS 11010-1	Passenger cars — Simulation model classification — Part 1: Vehicle dynamics Note: [Under Development]
ISO 10392:2011	Road vehicles — Determination of centre of gravity
ISO/AWI 5244	E-CCT (Electrochemical Cyclic Corrosion Test) Method For Automotive Chassis Part Note: [Under Development]
ISO 10521-1:2006	Road vehicles — Road load — Part 1: Determination under reference atmospheric conditions
ISO 10521-2:2006	Road vehicles — Road load — Part 2: Reproduction on chassis dynamometer

1.6 Life Cycle

1.6.1 Introduction

In the field of life cycle analysis, the standardization work related to FATIGUE4LIGHT is mainly developed at international level. The following committee has been identified:

- ISO/TC 59/SC 14 "Design life"

Meanwhile the European group CEN/SS S26 "Environmental management" has also interesting standards about this topic.

1.6.2 List of standards

Table 77 – Standards and project standards about Life Cycle

Reference	Document title
EN ISO 14040	Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Principles and framework (ISO 14040:2006)
EN ISO 14040:2006/A1	Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Principles and framework - Amendment 1
EN ISO 14044	Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Requirements and guidelines (ISO 14044:2006)
EN ISO 14044/A1	Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Requirements and guidelines - Amendment 1
EN ISO 14044/A2	Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Requirements and guidelines - Amendment 2
EN ISO 14045	Environmental management — Eco-efficiency assessment of product systems — Principles, requirements and guidelines
EN ISO 14046	Environmental management — Water footprint — Principles, requirements and guidelines
ISO/TR 14047	Environmental management -- Life cycle assessment -- Illustrative examples on how to apply ISO 14044 to impact assessment situations
ISO/TS 14048	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Data documentation format
ISO/TR 14049	Environmental management -- Life cycle assessment -- Illustrative examples on how to apply ISO 14044 to goal and scope definition and inventory analysis
ISO/TS 14072	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Requirements and guidelines for organizational life cycle assessment
ISO/WD TS 14074	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles, requirements and guidelines for normalization, weighting and interpretation
ISO/AWI 14075	Principles and framework for social life cycle assessment
ISO/AWI 59014	Secondary materials — Principles, sustainability and traceability requirements

2. CONCLUSIONS

After the analysis of the current standardization context at European and international levels, the following conclusion may be drawn.

There is a large number of European and international technical committees, as well as of standards and project standards related to Fatigue4Light project that may be useful for its development and also for its future dissemination. Although a specific standardization technical committee whose activity impacts directly the Fatigue4Light project has not been found, specific tasks to be addressed in the project are related with standardization works. Depending on the assessment by Fatigue4Light partners of the impact of the identified standardization committees on their tasks and the level of contribution that their results can represent for these committees, several actions can be performed.

With respect the dissemination activities, all the technical committees of this report have some relation to Fatigue4Light project, although probably the most relevant are those related to testing, manufacturing and electric vehicle.

3. REFERENCES

For the elaboration of this report, the following sources have been consulted:

- [1] CEN Website (www.cen.eu)
- [2] CENELEC Website (www.cenelec.eu)
- [3] CEN/CENELEC Projex Online database (projex.cen.eu) (restricted to authorized users)
- [4] EOTA Website (www.eota.eu)
- [5] ISO Website (www.iso.org)
- [6] ISO Project Portal (isotc.iso.org) (restricted to authorized users)
- [7] IEC Website (www.iec.ch)